

Terpenoids. Part LXXIX-Synthesis of α -Myrcene and Myrcenol

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α -Myrcene and myrcenol have been synthesised from the key intermediate 7 : 7-ethylenedioxy-1-octen-3-one obtained from ethyl 2-carbethoxy-5-ketohexanoate through a number of steps.

IN continuation of our earlier work on the synthesis of terpenoids through Wittig reaction¹⁻³, we have extended this approach to effect the synthesis of α -myrcene and myrcenol which forms the subject matter of the present communication. α -Myrcene, an acyclic mono-terpene, has not been found to occur in nature. However, it has been prepared by the vapour phase pyrolysis of myrcenyl acetate and iodine catalysed dehydration of linalool. It has been assigned the constitution (I) on the basis of its spectral data⁴.

No synthesis of this hydrocarbon seems to have been reported in literature. The present communication, however, records a clean synthesis of α -myrcene through the application of Wittig reaction with methylene phosphorane on appropriately substituted diketone for the fixation of isopropyleneic bonds (Scheme I).

with lithium aluminium hydride in dry ether to obtain the corresponding ketal-alcohol (V) which was oxidised with Collins reagent⁸ to afford 5 : 5-ethylenedioxy hexanal (VI) in 67% yield. Grignard reaction with vinyl magnesium bromide on ketal-aldehyde (VI) yielded secondary alcohol (VII) in 64% yield which upon oxidation with Collins reagent⁸ furnished α,β -unsaturated ketone (VIII). The ketal-ketone (VIII) upon deketalisation with *p*-toluene sulphonic acid in aqueous acetone⁹ solution under mild conditions resulted in the formation of 1-octen-3 : 7-dione (IX) in 62% yield.

The diketone (IX) was then submitted to the Wittig reaction¹⁰ with methylenetriphenylphosphorane when α -myrcene was obtained in 69% yield.

The identity of the compound was established through its IR and UV spectra by comparison with the one reported in literature⁴.

SCHEME I - α -MYRCENE

Ethyl 2-carbethoxy-5-ketohexanoate⁵ (II) on ketalisation with ethylene glycol in the presence of catalytic amount of *p*-toluene sulphonic acid⁶ produced ethyl 2-carbethoxy-5 : 5-ethylenedioxy hexanoate (III) in 70% yield. One of the carbethoxy groups of the substituted malonic ester (III) was eliminated by heating it with sodium cyanide in dimethyl-sulphoxide⁷, to afford the ketal ester (IV) in 63% yield. The ketal-ester was then reduced

Myrcenol, an acyclic mono-terpene tertiary alcohol was obtained by sulphuric acid catalysed addition to β -myrcene (Ia) and subsequent hydrolysis of the intermediate acetate. It has been assigned the constitution (XIII) on the basis of physical and chemical properties¹¹ and was later confirmed through a synthesis¹². The present studies report a new synthesis of myrcenol through the sequence of reactions employed as given in Scheme II.

The ketal-ketone (VIII) was subjected to Wittig reaction¹⁰ with methylenetriphenylphosphorane when

3-methylenec-7:7-ethylene-dioxy-1-octane (XI) was obtained in 67% yield. The ketal-diene (XI) was deketalised under mild conditions with *p*-toluene sulphonic acid in aqueous acetone⁹. The resulting ketone was subjected to Grignard reaction with methylmagnesiumbromide in anhydrous ether when it furnished myrcenol in 66% yield.

The identity of the synthetic alcohol was established through the comparison of IR and UV spectra with that reported in literature¹¹.

Experimental

Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer, Infracord Spectrophotometer with sodium chloride optics using a thin liquid film. The microanalyses were by L. K. Khullar.

Ethyl 2-carbethoxy-5:5-ethylenedioxy hexanoate (III) :

A mixture of ethyl 2-carbethoxy-5-ketohexanoate (II, 24 g.), ethylene glycol (9.7 g.) and *p*-toluene sulphonic acid (500 mg) in anhydrous benzene (500 ml.) was heated under Dean and Stark constant water separator until no more water collected in the limb. Thereafter, the contents were cooled, *p*-toluene sulphonic acid destroyed with 5% sodium carbonate solution and benzene layer separated. Washed the benzene layer with water, dried (anh. Na_2SO_4) and evaporated. Distillation of the residue under vacuum provided the ketal (III, 20 g.) in 70% yield, b.p. 195°/8 mm., η_D^{20} 1.4510 (Found : C, 57.27; H, 7.83. $C_{13}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 56.92; H, 8.08%) ν_{max} 2900, 1740, 1450, 1160, 1100, 1060, 950 and 860 cm^{-1} .

Ethyl 5:5-ethylenedioxyhexanoate (IV) :

A mixture of diester (III, 15 g.) and sodium cyanide (5.4 g.) in dimethylsulphoxide (100 ml.) was heated at 160° for 5 hr. The contents were cooled, poured in cold water and extracted with petroleum ether. The combined extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent expelled. The residue, upon distillation under reduced pressure afforded the monoester (IV, 7g) in 64% yield, b.p. 140°/6 mm., η_D^{20} 1.4365. (Found : C, 59.72; H, 8.64. $C_{10}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 59.38; H, 8.97%.)

ν_{max} 2980, 1730, 1450, 1180, 1110, 1050, 860 and 790 cm^{-1} .

5:5-Ethylenedioxy hexanol (V) :

To a fine suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (3.6 g.) in dry ether (400 ml) was added dropwise with stirring a solution of the monoester (IV, 10 g.) in ether (100 ml) so as to keep the ether at a gentle reflux. The reaction mixture was further stirred for 2 hr at 50° (bath temperature). Cooled the contents and poured into ice-cold solution of sodium sulphate. The product was extracted with ether and dried (anh. Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent followed by vacuum distillation afforded the ketal-alcohol (V, 6 g) in 75% yield, b.p. 124°/8 mm., η_D^{20} 1.4305. (Found : C, 60.35; H, 9.72. $C_8H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 59.98; H, 10.07%). ν_{max} 3400, 2950, 1650, 1450, 1140, 1060, 950, and 780 cm^{-1} .

5:5-Ethylenedioxy hexanal (VI) :

Chromium trioxide (25 g) was added in small instalments to a well cooled anhydrous pyridine (250 ml) with stirring. The contents were stirred further for 15 min after which the complex formed was separated by washing and decantation with petroleum ether (40°-60°). The yellow brownish complex was dissolved in dry methylene chloride (200 ml) and to this was added the alcohol (V, 6 g). After stirring for 15 min at 25°, the reaction mixture was poured into ice-cold water (100 ml) and the organic layer separated. It was washed with water, dried over anh. $CaCl_2$ and evaporated to remove the solvent. The residue was chromatographed over neutral alumina using petroleum ether (40°-60°) benzene mixture (5:1) as eluent. The product obtained was subsequently distilled under reduced rpressure to give the pure aldehyde (VI, 4 g) in 67% yield, b.p. 105°/8 mm., η_D^{20} 1.4510. (Found : C, 60.45; H, 9.25. $C_8H_{14}O_3$ requires, C, 60.74; H, 8.93%). ν_{max} 2950, 2725, 1740, 1390, 1325, 1260, 1155, 1125, 1070, 955 and 860 cm^{-1} .

7:7-Ethylenedioxy-1-octen-3-ol (VII) :

Grignard reagent was prepared to the exclusion of moisture from dry magnesium turnings (1.8 g), vinyl bromide (8.1 g) in dry THF (150 ml.). This was cooled in ice-cold water and the aldehyde (VI, 6 g) in THF (20 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring. After the addition was complete, the contents were left overnight at room temperature and, thereafter, the reaction mixture was heated under reflux for about an hour to complete the reaction. The cooled contents were decomposed with saturated solution of ammonium chloride. The organic layer was separated and aqueous phase extracted with ether (3×100 ml.). The total THF-ether extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent was removed. The residue was distilled under diminished pressure to obtain the allylic alcohol (VII, 4.5 g.) in 64% yield, b.p. 120°/8 mm., η_D^{21} 1.4660. (Found : C, 64.74; H, 9.49. $C_{10}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 64.49; H, 9.74%). ν_{max} 3450,

3080, 2950, 1650, 1450, 1155, 1070, 1045, 995, 920, 870, 790 and 755 cm^{-1} .

7 : 7-Ethylenedioxy-1-octen-3-one (VIII) :

The ketal-alcohol (VII, 2 g) was oxidised with pyridine chromium trioxide complex obtained from chromium trioxide (6.6 g) and pyridine (66 ml) in the manner described under VI. This was purified by chromatography over alumina eluting with 15% benzene-petroleum ether mixture and subsequent distillation under reduced pressure to obtain (VIII, 1.5 g) in 75% yield, b.p. 110°/8 mm., η_D^{21} 1.4700. (Found : C, 65.40; H, 8.57. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 65.19; H, 8.75%). ν_{max} 3080, 2920, 1680, 1640, 1420, 1240, 1195, 1170, 1125, 1060, 990, 920, 860 and 760 cm^{-1} .

1-Octen-3 : 7-dione (IX) :

The ketal-ketone (VIII, 1.5 g) was mixed with *p*-toluene-sulphonic acid (0.6 g), acetone (35 ml), and water (5 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for one hour at room temperature and thereafter the excess of PTS was destroyed by washing it with 5% sodium carbonate solution. The product was extracted with ether. The extract was washed with water and dried (anh. Na_2SO_4). After removal of the solvent, the residue was distilled under reduced pressure to furnish the ketone (IX, 0.7 g) in 62% yield, b.p. 100°/8 mm., η_D^{21} 1.4660. (Found : C, 68.68; H, 8.49. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 68.54; H, 8.63%). ν_{max} 3090, 2920, 1725, 1690, 1640, 1420, 1250, 1180, 1160, 1110, 990, 970, 900, 870 and 740 cm^{-1} .

2-Methyl-6-methylene-1 : 7-octadiene (I) :

The phosphorane was prepared from methyl-triphenylphosphonium iodide (12.1 g) in dimethylsulphoxide (40 ml), sodium hydride (1.5 g) in dimethylsulphoxide (15 ml) in nitrogen atmosphere. To this was added the diketone (IX, 1.2 g) in dry THF (10 ml). The contents were stirred and heated for 3 hr at 50° and left overnight. The contents were poured in crushed ice (200 ml) and extracted with petroleum ether (40°-60°, 3 \times 100 ml). The extract was dried (anh. Na_2SO_4), solvent was removed and the residue was purified by chromatography over neutral alumina and subsequently distilled under reduced pressure to furnish α -myrcene (I, 0.8 g) in 69% yield, b.p. 65°/15 mm., η_D^{21} 1.4718. (Found : C, 88.35; H, 11.52. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}$ requires C, 88.16; H, 1.84%). ν_{max} 3080, 2920, 1655, 1645, 1600, 1420, 1310, 1070, 990, 890 and 745 cm^{-1} , comparable to those reported in lit.⁴ at 1650, 1640, 1600 and 890 cm^{-1} .

UV spectrum $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{ethanol}} = 226 \text{ m}\mu$

Lit⁴ reports $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 224.5 \text{ m}\mu$.

3-Methylene-7 : 7-ethylenedioxy-1-octene (XI) :

Methylenetriphenylphosphorane was prepared from sodium hydride (1.6 g) in dimethylsulphoxide (16 ml) and methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (13.2 g) dimethylsulphoxide (32 ml) under nitrogen atmosphere. To this was added the ketal-ketone (VIII, 4.0 g) in THF (10 ml) below 15°. The contents

were stirred at room temperature for 2 hr and left overnight. Decompose it by ice-water and worked up as in (I). The residue left after removal of solvent was distilled under reduced pressure to afford ketal-diene (XI, 2.6 g) in 67% yield, b.p. 105°-108°/8 mm., η_D^{21} 1.5090. (Found : C, 72.15; H, 9.73. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 72.49; H, 9.96%). ν_{max} 3075, 2930, 1645, 1600, 1440, 1270, 1195, 1120, 1060, 990, 920, 880 and 750 cm^{-1} .

6-Methylene-7-octen-2-one (XII) :

The ketal-diene (XI, 2.4 g) was mixed with acetone (56 ml), PTS (0.96 g), water (7 ml) and stirred the mixture for 1 hr at room temperature. The excess of PTS was removed by washing it with sodium bicarbonate solution and worked up as in (IX). The residue left after removing the solvent was distilled under reduced pressure to obtain the keto-diene (XI, 1.2 g) in 66% yield, b.p. 95°/8 mm., η_D^{21} 1.5060. (Found : C, 78.61; H, 9.82. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$ requires C, 78.26; H, 10.14%). ν_{max} 3075, 2930, 1725, 1640, 1600, 1460, 1380, 1114, 985, 920, 890 and 745 cm^{-1} .

3-Methylene-7-methyl-1-octen-7-ol (XIII, myrcenol) :

To the Grignard reagent, prepared from magnesium (0.45 g) and methyl iodide (3.0 g) in dry ether (30 ml) was added dropwise the keto-diene (XI, 1 g) in dry ether (10 ml) and stirred the reaction mixture for one hr. After heating under mild reflux for 1 hr it was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The reaction mixture was decomposed with cold solution of ammonium chloride and worked up in a usual manner. The residue left after the removal of the solvent was distilled under reduced pressure to furnish the myrcenol (XIII, 0.6 g) in 66% yield, b.p. 90°-95°/10 mm., η_D^{21} 1.4475 (Found : C, 78.18; H, 11.54. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$ requires C, 77.86; H, 11.76%). ν_{max} 3400, 2940, 3070, 1800, 1640, 1600, 1450, 1390, 1195, 1160, 1130, 995, 910, 905, 890, and 740 cm^{-1} , comparable to those reported in Lit.¹¹ at 3390, 1802, 1630, 1597, 1198, 905, 901 and 893 cm^{-1} .

UV spectrum $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{ethanol}} = 225 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\epsilon = 14,800$)

Lit¹¹ reports $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{ethanol}} = 225 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\epsilon = 15,500$).

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